

ALGORITHMIC STAGES OF IMPROVING THE MENTAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS WITH THE HELP OF RAISING THE SCIENTIFIC WORLDVIEW

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Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of using educational technologies that are characteristic of the modern process of globalization, the formation of a student's readiness for life on the basis of pedagogical technologies, the need for successful socialization of the individual with constantly changing, increasingly interconnected pedagogical technologies.*

Keywords: *globalization, pedagogical technology, innovation, interactive method, outlook, business game, technology.*

The formation of a harmonious personality with intellectual potential, free and independent thinker, broad outlook, creative, loyal to our national team, necessitates the widespread use of the latest achievements of Science and technology in the field of education, thereby achieving competitive training of personnel that fully meets the requirements of World templates. Especially in this regard, the "national program of training of Personnel" is based on the fact that "the formation of an excellent system of training of personnel on the basis of the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, the achievements of modern culture, economy, science, technology and technology is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan" [6]

Attention was also further strengthened in the training of future primary school teachers. The purpose of this is: to prepare modern mature primary school teachers who will be able to educate their students in such a way that they have the ability to be intellectually potential, as well as to freely develop the abilities and abilities that are present in each of their students, to cultivate positive-behavioral qualities, national and civic feelings, which can, these experiments show that the implementation of the stated goal entails the solution of the tasks as follows:

- first of all, to approach the human factor in a new way, that is, to achieve the training of professionals capable of stabilizing the Justice and goodness that appear in the reader's soul, providing practical and spiritual support for the realization of the student's dreams of learning science;

- to achieve the training of specialists who can organize primary education, taking into account the modern requirements of world education for the development of primary education, relying on the rich spiritual and intellectual potential of our people and universal values;

-development of new pedagogical and information technologies in order to find optimal options for the organization of primary education and training of teachers who can make innovative approaches in the educational and educational work, which will be able to widely use them in practice;

-training of specialists capable of carrying out education and training in accordance with the content of education and the age of the student.

There are many positive changes in the field of Education corresponding to the development of our society, opportunities are born to study new and new aspects of our material and spiritual values. Today, a thorough study of national and universal values, the study and analysis of achievements in modern science, technology and technology are a solid scientific basis for expanding the scientific worldview of future specialists.

There is no doubt that in these days when our state gained independence, we will expand their spiritual and scientific worldview by instilling in the minds and hearts of the younger generation the rich heritage of our great-grandfather Amir Timur. Especially such qualities as the friendship of peoples, the struggle for peaceful coexistence, great creative work, respect for the piers and teachers, open volunteering, generosity, the ability to lend a helping hand to the poor will always give a trigger spirit and strength to the one who reads his work.

"Tukukiy Temurids", the eleven qualities that he adheres to in these structures, are not without benefit if we instill in the minds and hearts of our youth ideas in the field of education and education, consult with people from being entrepreneurs in the education of our youth, agree together with intelligent people who are sensitive and nurtured, and strengthen attention in the upbringing of

Amir Timur adhered to eleven of his qualities and twelve things in public administration for life. Thanks to this, was awarded respect, people's honor and high happiness. It has been an example in the emergence of such qualitative qualities as respect for people, kindness, patience and devotion to duty.

The rich heritage of the Great Amir Temur will be a solid spiritual foundation in the education and education of our students. Through them, the worldview of young people is regularly expanded, and naturally these also have a positive effect on their mental education. From our past, our rich scientific and spiritual heritage in this regard can be found as desired. Of course, the basis of mental education given to young people is the formed mind in them.

The most important qualities of the mind: depth, criticality, harmony, breadth, speed, freedom and solidity of thought. On the basis of these, the possibility of delving into the circumstances of the occurrence and development of things and phenomena, that is, communication-relations, and revealing patterns is created.

The development of intelligence: appeared and continued to develop in accordance with the living conditions (environment) of people and in the educational process. This development proceeds proportionally, depending on the development of the society in which a person lives, that is, the mentality of that society (family, community, state).

So, our ancestors, the generation of the distant past-our ancestors were also believers who dreamed of good intentions, perfection, they lived in pursuit of goodness, beauty, purity, knowledge.

Our past is rich in educated, intelligent great personalities, and from them today there is a wide opportunity to expand their scientific worldview in the mental education of young people.

Education and education based on information from works such as Amir Temur's "tracts", Nizamulmulk's "policy", Mirzo Babur's "Babur's", Gazizoda's "fertilizers for the ruler", as well as being able to assess their influence on the expansion of the spiritual worldview of students; on the basis of the above, to achieve the determination of promising directions in this work, etc. This requires great intellectual potential and professional maturity from future primary school teachers to in-depth study of what has been noted.

For this reason, it is advisable to use the achievements of computerization of educational processes in such processes. In order to effectively use modern computers in the educational process, it will certainly be necessary to scientifically substantiate the algorithmic system of the course of the same process [36,] and on this basis it is also possible to switch to optimal process control.

The results of our many years of scientific research in this area show that the future elementary school requires even greater intellectual potential (this is formed on the basis of mental education) than the teachers themselves, professional erudition (this is formed on the basis of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in a higher educational institution) and spiritual maturity (this is formed by expanding the

If we pay attention to the information that is used in the mental education of students, we will have to collect a very large amount of information in this regard, that is, it will be necessary to have a database on each of them.

So, the task now is to correctly understand the content of the above information, use the mind, create databases based on them, and divide them into systems suitable for the planned goals and objectives, create optimal options for their use in the educational process, develop methods, tools and ways. Of course, this is a large amount of work, and its solution requires a high intellectual potential from the researcher. Because the use of scientific and technological achievements in the development of society only accelerates the level of development. In this regard, D.Ashurova and Z. The following opinion of the Yuldashevs' is noteworthy: "according to the confessions of scientists from society, humanity is moving into a technocratic space in its development." On the basis of the principles of development in this space lies the introduction of the achievements of Science and technology on the basis of computer technology to all aspects of society's life as quickly as possible. The globalization of economic relations, the relativization of interstate borders under the influence of financial and information flows, as well as the extremely rapid introduction of the latest achievements in science into production and the creation of high-performance technologies are the cause of critical situations in relation to the individual: the informational renewal of the personality society occurs faster than the biological

Today, the computerization of education is a requirement of the era, it is difficult to find an area that did not use the achievements of Computer Science, and they also find their place as a reliable universal didactic tool and basis in various aspects of our life.

In this part of our work, we will cite a sequence of algorithmic stages of improving the mental education of students in raising their scientific worldview:

1. Information related to the direction (Mind, Mind, Science, Knowledge, perception, thought, scientific thought, New thought, thinking, creativity, creativity) and their types are determined;

2. Identification of the problem related to the direction (sharpening the mind ,giving mental training, forming a worldview, developing a scientific worldview) and their separation into systems, taking into account the data (data system) that they want to study;

3. The choice of the allocated systems suitable for the subject under study and the development of an algorithm suitable for it, that is, making the selected, that is, systematized data suitable for the blocks of the subject under study and bringing them to the appearance of information that is convenient to use;

4. Creation of a database on the topic under study and how to use them in what part of the topic;
5. Development of a control algorithm for their use, taking into account the subject under study (section, chapter, course, science) information bases and the Bank of information corresponding to it;
6. Scientifically-theoretically substantiating the full expression of the control algorithm to the object of research and its functional function;
7. Scientific and methodological analysis of the developed theoretical foundations and the creation of technology for their use in improving and developing the educational process;
8. Development of recommendations for achieving the selection of options that give a positive pedagogical effect;
9. To develop a criterion for their assessment in order to level the expansion of the scientific worldview formed in students according to the results obtained;
10. Analysis of the results of the technology of expanding the scientific worldview of students and preparation of a system of recommendations for the use of this technology in practical activities on their basis;
11. Covering the preferences of students with a broad scientific worldview in the penetration of creative activity and, on the basis of these, preparing guidelines and guidelines for attracting students in this direction;
12. Preparing future primary school teachers themselves to teach their students to creative thinking.

Now, based on the above sequences, we will give a brief overview of the functional function of each stage. Of course, it will be necessary to focus on the direction of the specialty that is being prepared in the mental education of future specialists and the expansion of their scientific worldview, otherwise we can get into the wrong way of expanding the scientific worldview of future specialists.

When expressing this algorithmic sequence X.A.T Raqulov's instructional information on "algorithmic stages of conducting scientific research" was used [26]. So, let's outline the tasks in the directions mentioned above.

Hence, the task of the first stage is as follows: only the human intellectual potential is collected relevant information and definitions of them. In this, a sequence is formed that corresponds to the mental maturation of a person, that is, the importance of intelligence, consciousness, perception, science, knowledge, thought, New thought, scientific thought, thinking, creativity, creativity, the process of creativity, the activity of creativity, talent, ability, talent, etc., in expanding the spiritual and scientific worldview of the individual is also prepared divided into systems. The purpose of this is to prepare information bases in the process of expanding the scientific worldview of students, making it convenient for them to use in education and training. It was also taken into account the use of these databases in mental education of students and young people.

The task of the second stage is to identify the problem related to the direction and determine the mechanism for using the databases of the first stage in the direction of solving this problem.

When introducing into practice the algorithmic system of expanding the scientific worldview of students, algorithmic blocks performing data collection, processing, storage, transmission perform the following functional tasks:

- to determine the imposition of the problem and to establish the scale of the issues to be solved in accordance with it, and to make it convenient to address it at any time;
- selection of the research object;
- scientific substantiation of the technology of the research process and creation of a mechanism for the preparation of information bases and the Bank of information corresponding to it;
- creation of criteria for collecting data corresponding to the purpose and object of the study and preparation of databases on their basis;
- to divide the prepared databases into systems suitable for Research tasks and create an algorithm for preparing information support based on them;
- determination of criteria, principles and algorithms used in accordance with the objectives and objectives of the study;
- to choose the methodology to be used and the appropriate educational technology and to achieve their improvement when it is found necessary;
- creation of a control algorithm to guarantee the optimal option for introducing the above functional tasks;
- preparation of the algorithmic system for implementation using the control algorithm.

This noted algorithmic system of expanding the scientific worldview of future primary school teachers is a universal methodology for finding optimal solutions to most problems in the field of education, and by making minor modifications, it can also be used to find optimal solutions to other similar problems.

The application of this algorithmic system to the learning process provides an opportunity to obtain the following advantages:

- provides an integral sequence of the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities in the expansion of the scientific worldview of students;
- guarantees the opportunity to create conditions for conducting classes at a high level and with high quality;
- provides an opportunity to use innovative methods of education and training;
- when conducting lessons, in the cooperation of teachers and students, not only new knowledge is mastered for the pedagogue, but also the student himself is looking for new knowledge in this, that is, he enters the creative process. In such activities, the student's passion for learning information related to this area is even greater;
- in this case, the student tries not only to fully master the content of the subject, but also to search for information related to this area. This is a creative activity, which is also a solid basis for the fact that the future primary school begins to expand the scientific worldview of teachers. Finding the optimal solution to the problem we are dealing with, in particular, the algorithmic system described above, necessitates future primary school teachers to use information technologies in their professional activities, and these can also serve as a powerful universal tool for future primary school teachers to independently acquire new knowledge in their professional activities. Especially the noted algorithmic system also forms the need and predisposition to the use of Information Technologies.

Therefore, in the next part of our work, we will devote to the development of a computer system that promotes the implementation of this algorithmic system in practice.

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